

Earthquake Disaster Risk Geographical Information System (GIS) for Banda Aceh City and Surrounding

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Abstract - The research objective is to design a geographic information system (GIS) that has the ability to perform zoning earthquake-prone areas in the city of Banda Aceh and surrounding from the peak ground acceleration (PGA) value. Using historical data and the occurrence of new earthquakes, the system automatically calculates the value of ground acceleration (PGA) and zoning prone areas from the point of the earthquake.

The methodology used in this study includes analysis and design methods. Analysis method consists of two stages namely stage of seismic data collection period 1973 - 2011 by magnitude more than 5 on the Richter scale and the calculation of the earthquake acceleration in bedrock using formula of the Crouse attenuation. Design method comprises several stages in a structured, namely designing data flow diagram (DFD), design entity relationship diagram (ERD), menu design, screen design and the design of State Transition Diagram (STD). Application developed using computer programming in ESRI ArcGIS software and visual basic programming language.

The primary conclusions of this study is that a local zoning earthquake disaster risk-based GIS can be built and developed with the approach to the calculation and classification of the peak ground acceleration (PGA) and by comparing the results with the zoning pattern of damage to buildings caused by earthquakes in 2004, there is a significant spatial relationship

Keywords: geographical information system (GIS), zonation, earthquake disaster risk, peak ground acceleration

I. INTRODUCTION

Since 1900, in Indonesia have been three incidents recorded major earthquake in 1983 the Banda earthquake with intensity 8.5 on the Richter scale, the 2004 Sumatra earthquake with intensity 9.0 on the Richter scale and the 2005 Nias earthquake with intensity 8.7 on the Richter scale. The intensity of this great earthquake, caused by the position of the Indonesian archipelago is geographically located between three major tectonic plates of the Eurasian plate in the north, the Indo-Australian plate in the south and the Pacific plate in the northeast. According with [13] and [9], inter-tectonic plate subduction associated with the earthquake event and movement in the bedrock.

Earthquakes in response to movement of the plates, besides resulting in loss of life also resulted in damage to

physical infrastructure. The total number of victims to this incident throughout the affected areas reached 186.983 42.883 people dead and missing [12]. In Indonesia, the highest recorded death toll in Aceh and North Sumatra on Sumatra earthquake in December 2004 with the toll reaching 110 229 people died, another 12,123 missing and 703,518 displaced people [6].

Damage to physical infrastructure of the most dominant earthquake damage to the building unit is either due to poor quality construction (internal). Figures damage to buildings caused by large earthquakes ever recorded are known to occur in the city of Banda Aceh in 2004 with a total damage figure of buildings accounted for 35 percent of all existing buildings [7]. The same condition also occurs in some cities, such as 140,000 units total buildings damaged by the earthquake in Yogyakarta in 2006 [5] and the numbers are much less damage to buildings due to Bengkulu earthquake of 2007.

Recognizing the geographical position of Indonesia and the fact that the earthquake gave a great impact both in terms of casualties and damage to infrastructure, particularly buildings, whereas up to now a more precise method to define areas prone areas in the earthquake damage to buildings is not yet available. This research aims to develop an application of geographic information systems (GIS) for the determination of earthquake risk zones, especially in the city of Banda Aceh and its surroundings by using the approach to the calculation of seismic acceleration in the bedrock or peak ground acceleration (PGA)

II. EARTHQUAKE AND EARTHQUAKE ACCELERATION

Earthquakes are the Earth's events due to release its vibrating energy in the earth suddenly marked with a fracture of rock layers in the earth's crust. Cause of the earthquake energy accumulation resulting from the movement of tectonic plates [2]. An earthquake with the magnitude large larger than 5.9 on the Richter scale are capable of damaging buildings in two ways through vibration that give direct horizontal force effect, and indirectly through liquefaction accident [8].

According to [12], the earthquakes can be caused by the presence of (a) tectonic force is closely related to the formation of fractures (faults), as a direct result of the interaction between the plates forming the earth's crust, (b) volcanic earthquakes associated with volcanic activity (c) the fall-out or a mass of ruins of rock / soil that are large (d) a conventional explosion and nuclear and (e) the impact of a meteorite collision. The cause of earthquakes caused by volcanic events, dropping / mass of rock debris, conventional and nuclear explosions and meteorite impacts is relatively rare and only affects a limited area.

Information about the characteristics of the acceleration in the bedrock by the earthquake (earthquake ground motion) can be obtained through the recording earthquakes in the past. Records of this acceleration can be integrated with the time to know the history of ground velocity and ground displacement. From the recording ground acceleration is possible to extract the characteristics of the ground motion recorded as peak ground velocity, peak ground displacement, ground motion duration and peak ground acceleration (PGA) [12]. Acceleration of the earthquake (ground velocity) can be calculated as an acceleration in the bedrock (ground acceleration) and acceleration of earthquake in the ground surface. Earthquake acceleration in the bedrock (PGA) can be calculated using function of attenuation. Attenuation function is a function which describes the correlation between the intensity of the local ground motion (a), earthquake magnitude (M), as well as the distance from a point in the earthquake source region (r). Geotechnical experts have formulated many attenuation functions. Attenuation functions that apply in one place may not necessarily apply in other places, because the functions highly dependent on natural conditions in a place [4]. There are two types of formulas attenuate function is the function of Joyner & Boore and function of Crouse to determine the acceleration of the earthquake in the bedrock in detail. Calculations of function of attenuation should be performed on all earthquakes. Changes in acceleration of the earthquake in the bedrock will impact directly on the acceleration of the earthquake at ground level

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology used in this study consisted of analysis methods and design methods. Analysis method consists of two stages namely stage of data collection and maps, and data processing stages. The data and maps used in this study is historical earthquake data of Banda Aceh and surrounding areas in the period of years 1973 - 2011 by magnitude more than 5 on the Richter scale (earthquake damage) which originate from the meteorology, geophysics and climatological office (BMKG) with a radius of the earthquake source 500 km from the city center as research conducted by [10]. Distribution of point sources of earthquake data points used in this study is as shown in Figure 1

Seismic data needed to calculate the value of earthquake acceleration in bedrock / peak ground acceleration (PGA). Earthquake acceleration in the bedrock is calculated by the use attenuase function. Attenuase function is a function which

describes the correlation between the intensity of the local ground motion, earthquake magnitude and distance of a point in the earthquake source area. In this study, the function Crouse attenuation [3] used to calculate the value of earthquake acceleration (PGA).

Figure 1. Distribution of Earthquake Sources Used For Data Research

Crouse attenuation formulas and functions can be described as follows:

$$\ln(\text{PGA}) = 6.36 + 1.76 - 2.73 \ln(R + 1.58e^{(0.068M)}) + 0.0091h$$

in where :

- PGA = Peak Ground Acceleration, gal
- R = Hipocenter distance, KM
- M = Earthquake Magnitude Moment
- H = Depth of Focus (Km)

PGA calculation will be done for every point in the area of 1000 x 1000 meters (gridding system) covers all research areas in the city of Banda Aceh and surrounding (Figure 2). The calculation will be done with the help of GIS software.

Figure 2. Distribution of 1000 x 1000 meters Grid and the Center of Grid

Zonation based on PGA values, prepared by the method of interpolation using the Kriging algorithm. The Zonation of PGA divided into several class values which contribute to the preparation of spatial analysis models. Design method is performed in this study is to design structured through several stages, namely the design of data flow diagram (DFD),

design entity relationship diagram (ERD), menu design, screen design and the design of state transition diagram (STD)

IV. IMPLEMENTATION AND DISCUSSION

GIS applications developed in this study has four main functionality is the function for addition of new seismic data of earthquake location and magnitude, the calculation of the distance from the earthquake source to the center of the grid in the city of Banda Aceh, the calculation of the acceleration of the earthquake at bedrock / peak ground acceleration (PGA) and earthquake hazard areas zonation

Untuk melakukan penambahan titik gempa baru, pengguna dapat menggunakan fungsi 'Go To XY' pada aplikasi dengan terlebih dahulu memasukkan koordinat titik terjadinya gempa baru. Setelah melakukan pengisian koordinat titik gempa baru, pengguna dapat melihat hasil penambahan data tersebut dan dapat ditampilkan di aplikasi dengan menggunakan fungsi 'Add Point'.

To perform the addition of new earthquake point, the user can use the 'Go to XY' on the application by first entering the coordinates of the point of a new earthquake. After making the coordinates of the point of charging a new earthquake, the user can see the result of adding the data and can be displayed in the application by using the function 'Add Point'. After the earthquake point to appear in the map, users must add the attribute of the earthquake event including date, time, magnitude and depth of the earthquake. To add attributes the earthquake, the user can simply press the menu button 'Add New Earthquake Point'. The whole updating process of the latest earthquake data is connected directly to the database system.

Application users can perform distance calculations between two points using the function 'hitung jarak'. The results of distance calculations required to calculate the value of PGA in the next step. Distance calculation process performed by calculating the distance the whole point of the earthquake, including a new earthquake point with the whole point of the grid in the center of city of Banda Aceh. From the results of these calculations, the shortest distance will be selected from the entire grid. The entire calculation is done automatically within the system, the calculation results are not displayed after calculations are complete but can be seen in the table attribute grid point. The results of the distance calculation will be changed to adjust the point of a new earthquake.

After calculating the distance, the next stage of the whole process is the calculation of the value of PGA. The calculation is done using the PGA Crouse atenuase function with a formula as described in the methodology. PGA value calculation performed on a separate module using the Field Calculator facilities is available in ArcGIS software. The overall results of the calculation of the value of PGA further integrated into the database application as can be seen in Figure 3. Relationships between entities in the database are described in a diagram relation as can be seen in Figure 4.

After the PGA calculation is completed, then the user can run up zoning by running the function 'Zoning Map' on the

application are available. The system will automatically perform zoning based on the calculation of the PGA. Distribution zones of the earthquake risk area in the city of Banda Aceh and surrounding areas are as shown in Figure 5

The difference in the color map shows the results of the different hazard zones based on the value of PGA in a certain range of values. The results showed that the city zoning Banda Aceh and surrounding areas consist of three levels of earthquake hazard zones including zone I with the

ID	Date	Origin Time	Longitude	Latitude	Depth	Magnitude
1	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
2	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
3	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
4	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
5	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
6	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
7	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
8	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
9	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
10	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
11	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
12	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
13	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
14	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
15	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
16	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
17	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
18	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
19	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
20	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
21	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
22	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
23	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
24	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
25	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
26	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
27	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
28	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
29	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
30	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
31	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
32	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
33	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
34	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761
35	81	14125.20094	70560.91305	62500.06020	13.4601	2.3761

Figure 3. Display Database in the Application

Figure 4 Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD) that describes the Inter-Entity Relationship Data in Databases

Figure 5 Distribution of Earthquake Risk Zones in the City of Banda Aceh Based on the value of PGA

PGA values in the range 0.25 - 0.4, zone II with a PGA value of 0.4 - 0.58 and zone III with the PGA 0.58 - 0.78 . Z

Previous research by the methods of sampling and measurement sites by [10] at specific locations in the District of Meuraxa (one of the districts in the city of Banda Aceh) showed that the PGA in the area between 0.325 to 0.40 gal with three zones namely micro-zone hard soil with the 0.325 PGA, middle-zone soil with a value 0.325 until 0.375 and PGA zone of soft soil (soft soil) with a PGA value of 0.375 up to 0.40 gal.

Comparison of the zones in the same area (District Meuraxa) between the results of this study with the value generated in the [10] study, PGA show zoning with a relative value approach, where most of the District Meuraxa zone is an area with PGA value ranges from 0.4 – 0.58 gal and a small area in the South, including the zone with PGA value ranges from 0.25 - 0.4 gal. The overall value of the zone in the district ranged from 0.25 to 0.58 gal. Comparison of the zoning study is as shown in Figure 6.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. PGA Zonation Comparison In Meuraxa Sub-District Using Atenuase Crouse (a) and Onsite-Seismic Classification by Sengara, 2008 (b)

An interesting fact of this zoning results if we compare the pattern of buildings that were totally damaged in the event of Sumatra Earthquake, 2004 [7] is that most of the buildings that were damaged, spatially located in zone II and III with a

relatively large range of values of PGA ranges from 0.4 - 0.78 gal. According with [7] Building units that suffered total damage is largely a function as a unit buildings with residential or commercial function. Research conducted by [9] and [1] are showed a similar relationship between the high value of the PGA and the impact caused damage to buildings in the event of an earthquake. Further research is needed to observe an empirical relationship between the zone of the PGA and other terrestrial parameters on the impact that may result if an earthquake in the area, especially at the level of damage to the building. The relationship between the PGA and the zoning pattern of the total damage to buildings caused by earthquakes can be seen in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Overlays between PGA Zonation and Distribution of Building with Totally Damage Level in the City of Banda Aceh.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the research objective, several conclusions can be drawn are:

1. GIS applications developed have the ability to manage, displaying history of seismicity information in the region of Banda Aceh and surrounding in the period 1974-2011.
2. Earthquake risk area based on geographic information systems can be built with the approach to the calculation and classification of the peak ground acceleration (PGA).
3. The system allows updates zoning PGA values based on incident/additional data on the most recent earthquake 500 km radiuses from the center of Banda Aceh and surrounding areas.
4. There is a significant spatial relationship between the pattern of the total damage to buildings on the Sumatran earthquake of 2004 with the zoning PGA value is relatively large.

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